

ALLICIN AS A POTENTIAL INDUCER OF APOPTOSIS IN CANCER CELLS

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Allicin is a major biologically active component, present in freshly sliced garlic bulbs (*Allium sativum*). It has been used by Indians, Greeks, Egyptians and Chinese to treat various diseases such as cardiovascular complications, arthritis, pulmonary congestions, abdominal over-growth, diarrhea and worm infestations.

Garlic extracts have been found to restrict active proliferation of cells during the episodes of skin, breast, uterine, cervix and colon cancer. It has anti-bacterial, anti-viral and anti-parasitic effects; it is also known to reduce platelet aggregation and induce apoptosis in tumor cells of different tissue origin due to the presence of many organosulphur compounds. It is presumed that apoptosis brings about cell shrinkage, chromatin condensation and stimulation of specific cysteine proteases known as caspase. Studies are underway to understand the mechanism that induces anti-proliferation and apoptosis in tumor cells.

Key words : Allicin, Anti-proliferation, Apoptosis, Cancer, Tumour.

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